

**THE METHOD OF EXPRESSING THE DIFFERENTIAL FORM OF THE LAW
OF ELECTROMAGNETIC INDUCTION****Mukhammadjon Turgunovich Xalilov****Professor, Andijan machine-building institute, Uzbekistan**

Abstract: This paper explains Faraday's law of electromagnetic induction through Maxwell's equations. In this case, the change of the magnetic field induction vector over time is equal to the magnitude of the electric field change in the rotor, and opposite in direction.

Key words: Electromotive force, voltage, current, magnetic field, electric field, rotor, divergence, magnetic flux.

Intraduction

Since the time of Galileo, the world has not seen so many wonderful and varied discoveries come out of one beginning, and probably will not see another Faraday again. A.G. Stoletov

Hans Christian Oersted, a Danish physicist, discovered in 1821 that a repulsive magnetic field is formed around a current-carrying conductor.

Repeating this experiment, the English physicist Faraday asked himself the following question: "if a magnetic field is formed around a current-carrying conductor, it is impossible to create a current in the conductor with the help of a magnetic field" [1-2].

In 1831, he finally discovered the law of electromagnetic induction.

Method

The meaning of this phenomenon is as follows: if we wind a conductor consisting of several copper wires in a coil, connect a galvanometer to the ends of the conductor, and move the permanent magnet inside the coil up and down, we see that the arrow of the galvanometer moves. So, as an electric current is generated in the windings of the coil, it is called an induced current (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The phenomenon of electromagnetic induction.

If we move a permanent magnet up and down on a coil with a galvanometer connected to it, then we observe that the arrow of the galvanometer moves in one direction when entering and leaving the magnet, and in the other direction when the magnet exits the coil. Therefore, the direction of the induced current changes depending on the movement of the magnet [3-5].

The stronger the magnet, the faster its movement and the greater the number of windings in the coil, the greater the amount of induced current.

If the magnetic poles are changed and moved, the deviation of the arrow also changes. Even if the permanent magnet is kept motionless and the coil is moved relative to it, an induction current is generated [6-8].

Let's see what the magnitude and direction of the induced electric force depend on the diagram below.

Figure 2. Magnitude of the induced electric force.

It can be seen from the figure that if the speed of the magnetic flux changes along the closed circuit, an induced electric force is created in the closed circuit, and its amount depends

on the speed of the magnetic current [9-11].

A closed circuit conductor has free electrons, we know that there is an electric field around the electron. An alternating magnet interacts with this field and creates an induction electric force.

When the current of magnetic induction changes from the surface bounded by a closed conductor, a current is generated in the conductor under the influence of the induced electric driving force. In it, Faraday's law of electromagnetic induction is defined using the following expression.

$$\varepsilon_i = - \frac{d\Phi}{dt} \quad (1)$$

The sign (-) in the formula indicates that the direction of the change of the magnetic flux is opposite to that of the induced electric force.

An electric current in a closed circuit is created as a result of the formation of an electric field. The electromotive force in a closed circuit is numerically equal to the work done as a result of the displacement of one unit of positive charge along the circuit:

$$\varepsilon_i = \oint_L E dl \quad (2)$$

Inductive electric power is determined in volts.

According to the definition of the magnetic induction current, it is expressed by the following formula:

$$\overline{\Phi} = \oint_S \vec{B} dS \quad (3)$$

Magnetic induction flux is measured in Webers.

If we add equality (1) to the above-mentioned expression (3), the following formula is obtained.

$$\varepsilon_i = - \frac{d}{dt} \oint_S B dS = - \oint_S \frac{\partial B}{\partial t} dS \quad (4)$$

Combining this equation with the expression for the work done as a result of moving along the contour, it looks like this:

$$\oint_L \vec{E} dl = - \oint_S \frac{\partial B}{\partial t} dS \quad (5)$$

The left side of the equation represents the flow along the contour, and the right side represents the flow along the surface. If we integrate the expression over the surface using the Stokes theorem, the following expression is formed [12-14].

$$\oint_S \text{rot} \vec{A} = \oint_L A dl \quad (6)$$

This allows expression (5) to be written as follows.

$$\oint_S \text{rot} \vec{E} ds = \oint_S \frac{\partial B}{\partial t} dS \quad (7)$$

In this case, since the surface is an arbitrary surface, the equation is written in this form:

$$\text{rot} \vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \quad (8)$$

In this case, the time-varying magnetic field induction vector from right to left creates a closed electric field intensity vector.

The negative sign in this equation is the velocity of the magnetic induction vector and the induced electromotive force generated in a closed loop is a left-handed screw system (Fig. 3).

Figure 3.

The above expression is called Faraday's law of electromagnetic induction in differential form written by Maxwell.

Conclusion

In short, the change of the magnetic field induction vector from right to left over time creates a closed electric field intensity vector, and when a variable electric current is supplied to a conductor or a coil, a current of a changing magnetic field is created in the coil, due to the fact that the changing magnetic field crosses the coil, a special induction electric force is created causes to be.

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